

Course: The Science of Skeletons:
Introduction to Bioarchaeology
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“We were at the entrance of the actual burial-chamber of the king...and as stone after stone was removed, and its gilded surface came gradually into view, we could, as though by electric current, feel the tingle of excitement which thrilled the spectators beyond the barrier”

- Howard Carter, The Tomb of Tutankhamen (1923)

Since the earliest days of archaeology, people have been fascinated by human skeletons recovered from ancient sites. However, skeletal remains are more than a physical bridge between the present and a romanticized past – they also encode valuable information about demography, gender differences, social identities and the daily lives of past peoples. Bioarchaeology is the study of human skeletal material from archaeological sites, and in this course students will identify the ways that bioarchaeologists use data collected from skeletal remains to estimate age and sex, diagnose ancient diseases, and examine activity levels and movement across prehistoric landscapes. Students will also critically evaluate how bioarchaeological discoveries are used in non-academic contexts, particularly focusing on their presence in museums and in the popular media.

Class Structure

Each week will begin with a hands-on lab or fieldtrip, exploring topics which include estimating age and sex, diagnosing ancient disease, examining activity levels, assessing ancestry and evaluating the presentation and treatment of archaeological human remains in museum contexts. Each lab or fieldtrip will be followed by an in-depth discussion of the implications of such methods for archaeological understandings of the human past. Importantly, this is not a human osteology class. While we will be covering features of important anatomical regions like the cranium and pelvis, and learning the basics of skeletal biology, there will be no analysis of fragmentary material or in-depth coverage of individual bones and teeth.

Readings

All assigned readings, news articles and blog posts will be posted as pdfs on CTools.

Grading

Grades will be based on four primary components: **1.** Attendance and Participation (20%); **2.** Weekly Quizzes (30%); **3.** Worksheets (25%); **4.** Individual Final Project (25%)

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during labs and fieldtrips, and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets, written assignments, and final presentations, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with U-M academic policy. You can read the Academic Conduct Code available online: <http://www.lsa.umich.edu/handbook/conduct.html>.

Grading Structure

Attendance and participation (20%): Every week an attendance sheet will circulate that you are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet – if you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. Full attendance for all 14 sessions of the course will guarantee 10% of this attendance grade (0.7% per class). However, simply showing up to class is not sufficient to achieve the full 20%. Focused and diligent participation in labs and fieldtrips, and active participation in group discussions will comprise the remaining 10% of this mark.

Weekly Quizzes (30%): Quizzes will take between 10-20 minutes of class time, and will take place on the second day of each week. These weekly quizzes will cover material learned the preceding week in class, and will range in structure from multiple choice, feature identification, and practical applications of knowledge learned during the course (e.g. estimate the sex of an individual, estimate stature using a femur).

Worksheets (25%): This class will comprise four labs and one fieldtrip to the Kelsey Museum of Archaeology. Each week you will be given a detailed worksheet that you are required to fill out. These worksheets will often outline specific tasks (e.g. estimate the sex of Cranium A), as well as areas of reflection or post-hoc critical analysis (e.g. What are some of the problems with the strategies bioarchaeologists use to estimate sex?). Worksheets from the preceding week will be due the first day of each week. Each worksheet is worth 5% of your course grade.

Individual Final Project (25%): The individual final project will have both a written and a presentation component. The written component will consist of an 8-12 page research paper that focuses on a bioarchaeological topic of your choice. Your topic must be drawn from one of four main categories that will be presented to you during the second week of class. You will need to choose a specific project topic and inform me of it by Day 7 (Week 4). Your project paper will be worth 20% of the final grade. It should draw from, and properly cite, peer-reviewed books and articles, using data outlined in these sources to present a central argument and critically evaluate the research that has been conducted on the topic thus far. During the final week of class, you will prepare a short presentation that summarizes your research for your peers. The length of this presentation will be determined once the add-drop period has ended and we have a final tally of students in the class. This final project presentation will be worth 5% of the final grade.

Class Schedule and Reading List

Week 1: Bad to the bone - the basics of skeletal biology

Day 1: What is bioarchaeology? Plus, anatomical terminology, and the biology of human bone and teeth.

- **Lecture:** Introduction to bioarchaeology, anatomical terminology, and respectful handling of human remains, and introduction to biology of human bone
- **Reading:** White 2000, Ch. 2

Week 2: All the single ladies - sex and gender in prehistory

Day 2: How bioarchaeologists estimate sex

- **Lecture:** Introduction to features of the pelvis and skull
- **Lab 1:** Estimation of Sex Using the Pelvis and Skull (*Worksheet 1*)
- **Reading:** Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; White 2000, Ch.17 (pp.363-365)

Day 3: Sex and gender in prehistory

- **Quiz 1:** Skeletal Biology Basics
- **Lecture and Group Discussion:** Unpacking gender in prehistory
- **Reading:** Stone 2012; Martin et al., 2010; Davis-Kimball 2002 (pp.36-66)

Week 3: What a drag it is getting old - age and social identity in the ancient past

Day 4: How bioarchaeologists estimate age [WORKSHEET 1 DUE]

- **Lecture:** Introduction to strategies for age estimation for adults and subadults
- **Lab 2:** Estimation of Age (*Worksheet 2*)
- **Reading:** Scheuer and Black 2004, Ch.1; White 2000, Ch.17 (pp.338-362)

Day 5: Age and social identity in bioarchaeology

- **Quiz 2:** Estimation of sex
- **Lecture and Group Discussion:** Understanding age and social identity in the past
- **Readings:** Moore 2009, Liston and Rotroff 2013

Week 4: Bone Broke – activity, disease and violence in the archaeological record

Day 6: Examining disease and illness in the past [WORKSHEET 2 DUE]

- **Lecture:** Introduction to paleopathology
- **Lab 3:** Paleopathology and trauma identification lab (*Worksheet 3*)
- **Reading:** White 2000, Ch.18 (pp.383-400)

Day 7: Violence in the bioarchaeological record

- **Quiz 3:** Estimating age
- **Lecture and Discussion:** The bioarchaeology of trauma
- **Reading:** Robbins Schug 2012, Baustian et al., 2012

Week 5: Better living through chemistry – isotopes and ancient diets

Day 8: Movement and diet in prehistory [[WORKSHEET 3 DUE](#)]

- **Lecture:** What dietary and strontium isotopes reveal about ancient diet and movements
- **Lab:** Ancestry, Stature and Dental Health Lab (*Worksheet 4*)
- **Reading:** Tykot 2006, Larsen 2011 (pp.418-19)

Day 9: Health and the transition to agriculture

- **Quiz 4:** Paleopathology and trauma
- **Video:** CARTA Agriculture's Impact on Human Evolution – C.S. Larsen ([Link](#))
- **Lecture and Group Discussion:** The costs and benefits of farming as a way of life
- **Reading:** Larsen 2011 (pp. 420-23, 426-43), Diamond 1984

Week 6: When the dead don't stay dead - the political and social lives of dead bodies

Day 10: The legislation and display of human remains [[WORKSHEET 4 DUE](#)]

- **Lecture:** Introduction to NAGPRA and the legislation of human remains
- **Fieldtrip:** The display of mummies at the Kelsey Museum of Archaeology (*Worksheet 5*)
- **Reading:** Scientific American 2012; Riding In 2004

Day 11: Bioarchaeology in the media

- **Quiz 5:** Isotopes and Ancient Diets
- **Lecture and Discussion:** What can we learn from the “gay caveman”, Richard III and “Romeo and Juliet”?
- **Readings:** The Daily Mail 2011, Johnson 2011, Williams 2013

Week 7: No *Bones* About It – The differences between bioarchaeology and Forensic Anthropology, + Final Project Presentations

Day 12: Forensic Anthropology – similarities and differences to bioarchaeology [[WORKSHEET 5 DUE](#)]

- **Quiz 6:** NAGPRA and Bioarchaeology in the Media
- **Lecture and Discussion:** Introduction to Forensic Anthropology
- **Video:** The Bone Detective □ □
- **Readings:** Byers 2008, Ch. 1.

Day 13: First half of student project presentations

Week 8: Final Project Presentations

Day 14: Second half of student project presentations

Schedule of Quizzes, Labs and Worksheet Due Dates**QUIZZES**

Quiz grades will make up 30% of your total course grade. Each quiz is worth 5%.

Number	Topic	Date
1	Skeletal Biology Basics	Thursday, July 9
2	Estimation of Sex	Thursday, July 16
3	Estimating Age	Thursday, July 23
4	Paleopathology and Trauma	Thursday, July 30
5	Isotopes and Ancient Diets	Thursday, August 6
6	NAGPRA and Bioarchaeology in The Media	Tuesday, August 11

SCHEDULE OF LABS AND FIELDTRIPS

The first day of Weeks 2-5 will have either a lab or a fieldtrip. Each week you will be given a detailed worksheet that you are required to fill out during the lab or fieldtrip.

Number	Topic	Date
1	Assessing Sex Using the Pelvis and Skull	Tuesday, July 7
2	Estimating Age	Tuesday, July 14
3	Paleopathology Identification and Stature Estimation	Tuesday, July 21
4	Ancestry, Stature and Dental Health	Tuesday, July 28
5	Field Trip to Kelsey Museum	Tuesday, August 4

WORKSHEET DUE DATES

Worksheets will make up 25% of your course grade. Worksheets from the preceding week will be due the first day of each week.

Number	Topic	Date
1	Assessing Sex Using the Pelvis and Skull	Tuesday, July 14
2	Estimating Age	Tuesday, July 21
3	Paleopathology Identification and Stature Estimation	Tuesday, July 28
4	Ancestry, Stature and Dental Health	Tuesday, August 4
5	Field Trip to Kelsey Museum	Tuesday, August 11

Reading List

- Baustian, K., R. Harrod, A. Osterholtz and D. Martin
2012 Battered and abused: Analysis of trauma at Grasshopper Pueblo (AD 1275–1400). *International Journal of Paleopathology* 2(2): 102-111.
- Buikstra, J., and D. Ubelaker (editors)
1994 *Standards for Data Collection from Human Skeletal Remains*. pp.15- 21. Arkansas Archaeological Survey Research Series, No° 44.
- Byers, Steven N.
2008 Introduction. In *Introduction to Forensic Anthropology*, 3rd Edition, pp. 1–27. Pearson: Boston.
- The Daily Mail
2011 The oldest gay in the village: 5,000-year-old is ‘outed’ by the way he was buried. *The Daily Mail*. Accessed 23 August 2014. ([Link](#))
- Davis-Kimball, J.
2002 *Warrior Women: An Archaeological Search for History’s Hidden Heroines*. Warner Books: New York.
- Diamond, J.
1987 The Worst Mistake in the History of the Human Race. *Discover*: 91–93.
- Johnson, E.M.
2011 The Allure of Gay Cavemen: Third genders, two spirits, and a media without a clue. *Wired*. Accessed 23 August 2014 ([Link](#)).
- Larsen, C.S.
2011 *Our Origins: Discovering Physical Anthropology*. 2nd Edition. W.W. Norton & Company: New York.
- Liston, Maria A., and Susan I. Rotroff.
2013 Babies in the Well: Archaeological Evidence for Newborn Disposal in Hellenistic Greece.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Childhood and Education in the Classical World*, 1–16.
- Martin, D.L., R.P. Harrod and M. Fields
2010 Beaten Down and Worked to the Bone: Bioarchaeological Investigations of Women and Violence in the Ancient Southwest. *Landscapes of Violence* 1(1): 1-19
- Moore, A.
2009 Hearth and Home: The Burial of Infants within Romano-British Domestic Contexts. *Childhood in The Past* 2(1):33-54

Riding In, J.

2004 Decolonizing NAGPRA. In *For indigenous eyes only; a decolonization handbook*. Cavender Wilson, A. and M. Yellow Bird (Eds.), pp.53-66, School of American Research, Santa Fe.

Robbins Schug, G., K. Gray, V. Mushrif-Tripathy, A.R. Sankhyan.

2012 A peaceful realm? Trauma and social differentiation at Harappa. *International Journal of Paleopathology* 2(2): 136-147.

Scientific American (editors)

2012 Who Owns the Past? *Scientific American*, published 27 March 2012 ([Link](#)).

Tykot, R.H.

2006 Isotope Analyses and the Histories of Maize. In *Histories of Maize: Multidisciplinary Approaches to the Prehistory, Linguistics, Biogeography, Domestication, and Evolution of Maize*, edited by John E. Staller, Robert H. Tykot, and Bruce F. Benz, 131 – 142. Amsterdam: Elsevier Academic Press.

Scheuer, L. and S. Black

2004 *The Juvenile Skeleton*. Elsevier, Amsterdam.

Stone, Pamela C.

2012 A Bioarchaeology of Sex and Gender: What is the Difference and Why is it Important? *The SAA Archaeological Record* 12(2): 38-40.

White, T. and P. Folkens

2000 *Human Osteology*, 2nd Edition. Academic Press, San Diego.

Williams, H.

2013 What is truly wrong about digging up Richard III? *Archaeodeath*. Accessed 23 August 2014. ([Link](#))